

Seroprevalence of Transfusion Transmissible Infections among Emergency Blood Donors at Trauma Blood Centre in Jaipur, RajasthanParmendra Pachori¹, Radheshyam Kumawat^{2*}, Saroj Pachori³, Moullik Pachori⁴¹Senior Professor, Department of Immuno-Haematology & Transfusion Medicine, S.M.S.M.C., Jaipur²PG Student MD IHBT (Resident Doctor), Department of Immuno-Haematology & Transfusion Medicine, S.M.S.M.C., Jaipur³Senior Professor, Department of Pathology, S.M.S.M.C., Jaipur⁴MBBS Student, M.G.M.C., Jaipur

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Transfusion of the blood is associated with various risks such as transmission of dangerous diseases including HIV, hepatitis and STIs. These transfusion transmitted infections can be prevented by thorough screening, however, to screen the samples available, it is necessary to understand the prevalence of these diseases in a particular geographical region. The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of “transfusion transmissible infections” at a blood centre affiliated with tertiary care hospital and medical college.

Material and Method: A retrospective study examining the prevalence of TTIs among emergency blood donors was conducted at the Trauma Blood Center from January 1, 2022, to December 31, 2022. The data of 13,160 donor samples was retrieved from the blood centre's database using a checklist. ELISA tests were run for HIV I&II, HBsAg, HCV and other tests to screen for syphilis and malaria. Data analysis was done using SPSS Version 20, the significance of the prevalence was determined by using p-value.

Results: During the study period, a total of 13,160 emergency donors of blood were recorded, with the majority being male. Among these donors, 228 were tested reactive for “transfusion-transmissible infections” (TTIs), including 13 cases of HIV I/II, 153 cases of HBsAg, 25 cases of VDRL, 0 cases of MP and 41 cases of HCV. The prevalences of the TTI were: HIV 0.098%, HBV 1.16%, HCV 0.31%, syphilis 0.19%, and malaria 0%. Among the 228 positive donors, 118 were in the 18-30 years age group, 81 were in the 31-40 years age group, 29 were in the 41-50 years age group, and none were in the 51-60 years age group.

Conclusion: Given that donors of blood are typically viewed as a representative sample of a healthy population, the prevalence of “transfusion-transmissible infections” (TTIs) among donors serves as a noteworthy indicator of these infectious agents within our apparently healthy community.

Recommendation: Targeted initiatives such as pre-marital counseling and testing, as well as immunization campaigns with the Hepatitis B vaccine, should be directed towards populations deemed at high risk.

Keywords: Prevalence, Blood transfusion, Transfusion transmitted infection, National Blood Transfusion Service, Hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, HIV.

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Introduction

Ensuring blood safety is paramount in transfusion medicine. TTIs can be dangerous considering the safety of the blood transfused and represent a serious public health concern. [1] An individual with latent infection stage can cause the transfer of disease, leading to a potential increase in infections within the population through transfusions. Unsafe blood transfusions incur substantial costs to the patients who receives the blood and to the healthcare system as a whole. Testing the blood for TTIs is important to ensure safety during blood transfusion [2]

Transfusion of the blood, while essential for saving lives, carries the potential for transfusion of

dangerous diseases. Donors serve as the backbone of a secure blood and blood product supply. [3] The consequences of blood transfusion complications range from mild to severe, and in some cases, can even be fatal. Therefore, rigorous testing before the transfusion is necessary to ensure the efficacy of blood transfusion process. [4] These infections pose a significant threat to the safety of blood transfusions, necessitating that blood transfusion services prioritize the provision of safe, sufficient, easily accessible, and efficient blood supplies across all levels. Transfusion can lead to transmission of hepatitis and other sexually transmitted diseases which can be prolonged bacteremia and the establishment of carrier or latent

states within individuals. Moreover, these infections are associated with fatality and mortality. It is noteworthy that approximately 12.5% of patients who undergo “blood transfusions” face the risk of contracting “posttransfusion hepatitis”. [5] In order to mitigate the risk of “transfusion-transmitted infections” (TTIs), it is imperative to meticulously select donors to ensure the safety of blood products and prevent collection from individuals who may potentially carry infectious agents. Assessments of TTIs are crucial for evaluating the “blood safety” and monitoring the effectiveness of existing screening protocols.[6] The primary objective of the current study was to investigate the prevalence of TTIs among healthy donors of blood at a tertiary care hospital.

Materials and Methods

The research was a sort of secondary analysis of the results. Blood donation data from 1 January, 2022 to 31 December, 2022 were taken into analysis.

Place of Study: Department of Immunohematology & transfusion medicine, Blood center of SMS Medical College and attached hospital Jaipur.

Study Period: In a period of a year from January 2022 to 31 December 2022.

Study Type: Retrospective study.

Study Universe: All emergency Voluntary blood donors coming to Trauma blood center SMS hospital jaipur.

Study Population: It will be decided by applying inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria: Volunteers above 18 years and below 60 years with no illness, STI’s, and liver

diseases with haemoglobin more than 12.5g/dL and weight above 45kg were included in this study.[7]

Exclusion Criteria: People with any STI, risky sexual habit, drug abusers, chronic disease, and pregnant ladies were not included in this study

Kits used for screening the transfusion transmissible disease included “HCV, HIV, HBsAg, malaria, and syphilis”. The commercial name of the kits were as follows:

1. HIV- J.Mitra, Meril (4th generation)
2. HbsAg- Meril, J. Mitra (3rd generation)
3. HCV- Meril, J. Mitra (3rd generation)
4. VDRL- Tulip (Rapid Plasma Reagin)
5. Malaria- Mitra Lateral flow rapid card test

Testing was carried out for all emergency blood donors before blood transfusion to screen the transfusion transmissible disease. ELISA was performed for detection of HIV; RPR for detection of syphilis. Rapid test kits were used for malaria parasite. The protocols given by manufacturers was used to determine control, cut-off value and procedures

Results

During the study period total emergency blood donors 13160 among these most of male donors and found 228 TTI positive among these 13 HIV, 153 HBsAg, 25 VDRL, 0 MP, and 41 HCV positive.

The prevalence of the TTI in the serum were as follows, HIV 0.098%,HBV 1.16%, HCV 0.31%, syphilis 0.19% , and 0 % malaria. Total of 228 donors was positive among these 118 18-30 yrs, 81 31-40yrs,29 41-50yrs and zero 51-60yrs age group were positive.

Figure 1: TTI Seroprevalence

Figure 2: No. of TTI positive

Discussion

Blood transfusion is considered lifesaving procedure. Nevertheless the risk of the associated transfusion transmitted diseases can prove to be fatal for the patients with existing illness. It is necessary to determine the prevalence of such disease before the transfusion. Such disease might be in a latent form but the donor can act as vector for this disease which can eventually occur in patients who receive such blood. To understand the prevalence and the demography of the disease existing in patient which can be transmitted via blood transfusion studies are conducted to determine the seropositivity of the blood donors. In this study the TTI's are determined by conducting test for the potential diseases in blood donor.

In our study it was found that the majority of the age group that had seropositive results belonged to 18-31 years of age. This finding is similar to the study conducted by Koshy, et al (2014) [8]. This is explained by the fact stated by Karmakar et al (2014) that this age group engages in risky sexual activities that might cause transmission of sexually transmitted disease [9]. Also, most of the patients that were found seropositive were males, similar results have been reported Choudhary, et al (2007) [10]. The blood donors were majorly males, this is due to high prevalence of anemia amongst females and lower levels of hemoglobin they could not participate in blood donating activities.

A total of 228 donors were found to be seropositive amongst 13160 donors. Hepatitis B was the most prevalent disease in seropositive patients. Other studies conducted by Chatteraj et al (2008) , Kaur et al (2004), Singh B (2001) et al and Giri et al (2012) reported hepatitis B as the most prevalent [11,12,13,14]. The second highest seropositive results were of hepatitis C. Hepatitis C is blood borne disease and it increases the probability of hepatic carcinoma. 0.098% of the seropositive cases belonged to HIV. This finding is comparable in Koshy, et al (2014) and Mandal, et al (2016) [8, 15] while it is contradictory with Kaur, et al and Sabharwal, et al [16,17]. This is because the people with HIV positive blood varies as per the population under study and other demographical factors. However, syphilis a dangerous sexually transmitted disease was found 0.19% in the study population.

Conclusion

Blood donors are generally considered as healthy individuals by the prevalence of the latent infectious agents indicates the prevalence of these diseases.

Recommendation: Pre-marital counselling and testing, Immunization with Hepatitis B vaccine must be targeted to the high risk population.

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